

A new switching power supply circuit based on Schmitt trigger

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Compared with traditional linear power supplies, switching power supplies have the advantage of high efficiency, but the circuit is complex. It needs oscillation unit and pulse width modulation unit. This paper introduces a new switching power supply circuit using the Schmitt trigger. The new circuit is based on the linear power supply circuit. It does not contain oscillation and pulse width modulation unit. It directly uses the continuous feedback signal as the input of Schmitt trigger, and the output of Schmitt trigger is used to control the switch.

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the linear power supply. Its basic principle is the negative feedback. When the output voltage is higher than the set value, the output voltage of the opamp A decreases and the voltage of the emitter of Q decreases, so that the output voltage decreases. If the output voltage is lower than the set value, the process is just the opposite, so as to achieve the stabilization of the output voltage.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the linear power supply

We add four components to the linear power supply circuit and design a new switching power supply circuit, as shown in Figure 2. The components added include an inductor L, a diode D, a capacitor C and a Schmitt trigger T. L, D and C are the basic elements necessary for ordinary switching power supply circuit, and their

functions are the same as those in ordinary switching power supply circuit. The Schmidt trigger T is the core control element of our new switching power supply circuit. It can turn the continuous feedback signal into switching signal and control the on and off of Q, so as to realize the function of switching power supply. The basic negative feedback principle of the new circuit is consistent with figure 1, but due to the existence of the Schmidt trigger, Q does not work in the continuous mode, but in a switching mode.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of the new switching power supply circuit based on the linear power supply circuit

Figure 3 shows the practical circuit diagram. The input voltage is 15V, the output voltage is 5V and the load current is 2A. The operational amplifier U1B with resistors R5, R6 and R9 forms a Schmitt trigger. In Figure 3, U1A is an in-phase amplifier, while U1B constitutes an inverse output Schmitt trigger, which is slightly different from Figure 2. In Figure 2, opamp A is an inverse amplifier while T is an in-phase output Schmitt trigger.

Figure 3 Practical circuit of the new switching power supply

Figure 4 shows the simulation results. The blue line represents the output voltage waveform and the red line represents the current waveform of Q1. The operating frequency of Q1 is about 1.8kHz, and the maximum current of Q1 is about 6.2A. The output voltage ripple is about 2.4V.

Figure 4 Simulation results of the practical circuit of the new switching power supply ($L1=220\mu$, $C1=220\mu$)

In order to reduce the voltage ripple, we changed $L1$ and $C1$ to simulate. Figure 5 shows the results when $L1 = 470\mu$ and $C1 = 220\mu$. The frequency is about 1.4kHz, the maximum current of Q1 is about 5A, and the output voltage ripple is about 2.3V. It can be seen that increasing $L1$ will reduce the frequency and the maximum current of Q1, but it is not helpful to reduce the output voltage ripple.

Figure 5 Simulation results when $L1 = 470\mu$ and $C1 = 220\mu$

Figure 6 shows the results when $L1 = 220\mu$ and $C1 = 470\mu$. The frequency is about 1.45kHz, the maximum current of Q1 is about 6.7A, and the output voltage ripple is about 1.5V. It can be seen that increasing $C1$ can significantly reduce the output voltage ripple.

Figure 6 Simulation results when $L1 = 220\mu$ and $C1 = 470\mu$

In order to reduce the output voltage ripple, Figure 7 shows the improved circuit. The circuit adds a small resistor $R10$ (0.05 Ohm) and increases $C1$ (10000uF). Figure 8 shows the simulation results. The frequency is about 3kHz, the maximum current of the switch is about 4.2A, and the output voltage ripple is only 20mV. The calculation of power shows that the output power of $V1$ is about 16W, the absorbed power of $R1$ is about 9.5W, the absorbed power of $Q1$ is about 5W, and the absorbed power of the diode is about 1W. Its efficiency is not high, about 60%.

Figure 7 the improved circuit

Figure 8 Simulation results of the improved circuit

In order to improve the efficiency, we give the circuit shown in Figure 9. The circuit uses a PNP transistor as the switch, which reduces the voltage drop when conducting, so as to reduce the power consumed by the switch. The input voltage is 24V, the output voltage is 12V and the load current is 1A. Figure 10 shows the results. At this time, the output power of V1 is 13.7w, the absorbed power of load resistor R1 is 11.6w, and the efficiency is about 85%. The switching frequency is 1.35kHz, and the maximum current of the switch is about 4.4. The on time of the switch is 0.18ms.

Figure 9 High efficiency circuit

Figure10 Simulation results of the high efficiency circuit (the load current is 1A and the input voltage is 24V)

We also change the load current and input voltage to simulate the circuit shown in Figure 9. The results are shown in Figure11 and Figure12. Figure 11 shows the results when the output voltage is 24V and the load current is 3A. The frequency is about 1.65kHz and the maximum current is 6.9A. When the load current increases, the frequency increases, the proportion of conduction time in a cycle also increases, and the maximum current also increases. The on time of the switch is about 0.28ms, which also increases. Figure 12 shows the results when the input voltage is increased to 36V and the load current is 1A. The frequency is about 0.57khz and the maximum current is 7.94A. The frequency decreases, the conduction ratio decreases and the maximum current increases. The conduction time is 0.17ms. When the input is 36V, the value of L1 should be increased. The maximum current can be reduced. The simulation results show that when L1 is 1000uH, the frequency is 0.6khz, the maximum current of the switch is 5.3A and the conduction time is 0.23ms

Figure 11 Simulation results when the load current is 3A and the input voltage is 24V

Figure 12 Simulation results when the load current is 1A and the input voltage is 36V

For the first time, we have proposed a new switching power supply circuit. The circuit is based on completely different working principles. There are still some problems in the theoretical analysis, performance improvement and practical application of the circuit.